

THE ACT OF ORAL COMMUNICATION IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Annotation

The thesis deals with the lexical, grammatical features of oral communication in English and Uzbek languages. Furthermore, the work is illustrated with sample.

Key words:

Oral communication, communicative action, spoken language, communication style, Communicative language Teaching (CLT), law.

Introduction

The central tenet of speech act theory is the idea that humans use language to perform a communicative action, such as to greet or invite someone, or to offer something (Searle, 1969). However, traditional approaches to language teaching tend to focus on form and accuracy rather than on the context and purpose of the speech act. This approach emphasises what speakers say rather than what they intend to communicate.

Jenny: Would you like to have a coffee?

Kiril: Sorry, I have a class now and then an assignment to finish.

Jenny: What time does your class start?

Jenny's response is accurate, and appears to be on topic. However, it is inappropriate for the situation, because it suggests that she didn't understand Kiril's remark as a negation, nor the importance of the word now in his statement. A more appropriate response to Kiril's remark might be to suggest another day or time that suits him better.

According to holistic view, Boxer and Pickering (1995) examined how English textbooks present examples of speech acts, focusing on complaints. Their research shows that, in the textbook examples, direct complaints are more common than indirect complaints, although indirect complaints are more common in authentic situations. While the context and the relationship between the speaker and the addressee hugely influence language choices, this information is rarely present in textbooks (Boxer & Pickering, 1995). As it is impossible for teachers to cover all possible situations, it is important to

introduce learners to the idea of language use in context, and to how different contexts influence language choices.

Theory and practice

Teachers can introduce students to various speech acts, such as accepting or refusing an invitation, congratulating, or expressing disappointment. Within the Communicative Language Teaching approach, these functions are presented within a particular topic/theme, and not in isolation. In the topic of health, for example, teachers can introduce students to the relatively formal language used for making an appointment over the phone. Using a more authentic English resource can lead to discussions of how the speakers negotiate the amount of information they provide, and the formality of the language they use. This can change as the conversation progresses. Because the way a function is expressed in language differs depending on the context and relationship between the speaker and addressee, it is important to also help learners be aware of other aspects of communication. This implies that teachers could ask learners to think about how might a making a doctor's appointment differ from making a dinner appointment with a friend.

Spoken language is the language of speech, sound and sound became a product of speech activity through articulation, as well as combination and sentences said by the interlocutor pronunciation support, with or without conversation, technical tools a certain person in a certain place and time who is free from them. A social group reflects the cultural and social characteristics of a people is a lively and active language in use.

The text of oral communication (to communicative linguistic theories mainly we suggest to call it the discourse of oral communication) – speech communication goal, opinion of the interlocutor in communication activities a word, a phrase, a sentence, or a whole, which embodies the relationship is a linguistic expression in the form of a text, the content of which corresponds to the topic is an expression. The discourse of oral communication is appropriate to the communication situation warning, message - informant, command, desire, desire, question is a linguistic unit that performs functional tasks such as an answer;

Oral communication style (verbal communication style in some studies used as) - words, words in people's daily social activities discourse types created using combinations, sentences, conversation, communication, meeting, discussion, presentation, TV and Internet communications, public speech, based on TV and video conference, interviews and daily needs. The question that arises

is a specific type of communication in the form of an appeal and an answer based on laws and norms freely, i.e. officially is carried out in an informal manner.

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